

A Study on Online Consumer Behaviour with Regards to Youths of Bangalore

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Abstract

Consumer behaviour is the study of individuals, groups, or organizations and all the activities associated with the purchase, use and disposal of goods and services, including the consumer’s emotional, mental and behavioural responses that precede or follow these activities. This study is mainly done with respect to the perception of youth of Bangalore. The sample size of the data collected is 109 respondents, where some of them were students whereas, the others were employed or working in different fields. Secondary data was collected from research papers, journals, magazines and websites and books. The Analysis also suggest that online shopping can be increased by quality improvement and after sales performances. Youths in Bangalore use Flipkart the most for online shopping and they have prefer offline shopping as majority faced issues such as low quality and change of product, and many more.

Introduction

Nowadays online shopping has bought a new trend in the field of shopping from A to Z products. It has also reduced the burden on customers where they physically travel to buy things. It is an easy solution for busy life in today’s world. Through online shopping customers can buy many products such as designer dresses, footwear, electronic gadgets, toys, gifts, jewellery, Beauty products, books, stationaries etc. Online shopping enables the customers to choose from the various alternatives possible with better prices and easy price comparison to find the better deal. It has obtained most popularity in the 21st century as it enables the customers to shop with a touch in their busy life. As per the research made most of the respondents have responded in favour of online shopping sites. The respondents prefer to shop online because it reduces the time involved in shopping as well as it eliminates the intermediary services. Online shopping also provides after sales services as traditional shopping does therefore it is convenient to the customers to buy and return if the product are not satisfactory. Online shopping is a drawback for those who are uneducated or illiterate and for those who are unaware of these kind of services available. Shopping online also creates some privacy issues where people hack the bank account details in shopping. As per the research made by the researchers, it is clear that the customer’s will to buy online products is increasing day by

day with the increase in the number of online shopping sites. Therefore online shopping spreads a kind of awareness to the customers as and when the new products arises. Online shopping has also made an advancement in the field of shopping medicines where people need not have to buy their medicines physically, rather it would be delivered to your footsteps.

Objectives

- To know the perception of consumers choice regarding online and offline shopping.
- To know what chances are to be made to improve online shopping
- To know the problems faced while online shopping
- To identify the suggestions to improve online shopping in India.

Review of literature

1. Islam Rahman (2018) in his research paper on online consumer behaviour in Bangladesh has highlighted that increases in the use of mobile phones and internet has influenced the ordinary citizens to shops using online websites. The paper focused on how ordinary citizen are influenced towards online shopping people’s attitude towards online shopping, reason for choosing online shopping. The methodology adopted to understand the behaviour of online shopping is through a self-constructed questionnaire of 160 respondents from Dhaka city. The author found that consumer shop online to save time and for the options that is available to choose among various alternatives. The paper also found that both male and female have same attitude towards online shopping.
2. Kumar Amith (2014) in his research paper on the study of people’s attitude towards online shopping. The author’s present paper is based on the assumption of classical model behavior. The paper focused on the study of consumer perception and behavior towards online shopping. The author has also highlighted that people are shopping through internet is because shopping through online is time saving and convenient. The methodology adopted to collect the data includes both primary and secondary. Primary data was collected by means of survey. The author found that online shopping is getting popular among young generation as they feel it more comfortable, time consuming and convenient. The paper also found that when individual decided to make online purchase he/she will be affected by multiple facts.
3. Kaur Anupreet(2016) in her research paper on study of behavior of consumer towards electronic shopping. The authors has highlighted that internet is growing rapidly during the past decade, especially online shopping is rapidly growing in e-commerce are. The paper identified that people moving towards towards electronic shopping because of easy availability of internet access both at work place and at home. The paper focused to establish a preliminary assessment evaluation and understanding of the characteristics of online shopping. The methodology adopted to collect the data is through primary and secondary source. The primary data was collected through questionnaire. The paper found that most of the online shopping use internet for searching product information.
4. Dani Jimila (2017) in her research paper online consumer behaviour, the author explained that due to the innovation and modernization in technology online shopping is gaining more importance and becoming more popular in the minds of general public. The paper focused on factors influencing the consumer to shop online and also to find out who are online shoppers in terms of demography. The paper is a descriptive as well as survey research. The author has used both qualitative and quantitative research methods. The paper found that price of the product and services and discount is the important factor that influence customer to shop online. Convenience is another important factor that influence to go for online shopping.

5. Wuhil Normilia and Nadra Nurul (2018) in their paper on major concerns towards online shopping. The study aims to provide the needed information to understand the barriers for university students to shop online. The methodology adopted to collect the data is through self-Administered questionnaire. The main findings of this study are that non online shoppers are unlikely to buy online as they prefer to shop traditionally and self-users the quality of the goods before they buy their study also emphasis that traditional sellers provides better customer services and employ better sales person.

Research Methodology

The research is based upon primary data and secondary data both. The primary data was collected through a questionnaire which was designed exclusively for the study.

The sample size of the data collected is 109 respondents, where some of them were students whereas, the others were employed or working in different fields. The secondary data was collected from research papers, journals, magazines and websites and books.

Analysis

- To know the perception of consumers choice regarding online and offline shopping.

As per the analysis, it is clear that among the 109 respondents, most of the respondents prefer offline shopping due to many reasons such as delay in delivery time, the quality of goods and other factors.

- To know what chances are to be made to improve online shopping

From the above graph, it is clear that most of the respondents have answered that the quality of products should be given most priority that is 80.7% of them have same opinion. Some respondents think that delivery of time of the product should be given importance that is 33.9% of them think as such, whereas, some prefer that the choices of goods should be given more priority. 31.2% of respondents have answered that services after the delivery of products should be given priority whereas, 0.9% of respondents feel that all the above categories should be given priority.

- To know the problems faced while online shopping

What is the most common issued faced while online shopping?

109 responses

quality
Nothing
Server
Quality
Return policy
quality difference
Delivery time
Quality
Delivery
Shoes
Delivery date
Nice

Out of 109 response the major issues faced by customers are like some customers are not satisfied with the quality, unsatisfactory issues related to product return policy, finding very difficult in quality issues and differences, online traders delay in delivering product on certain date and time, customers are not satisfied with the Network as it shows server busy many times when they are in need of products.

- To identify the suggestions to improve online shopping in India.

Do you have any suggestions to improve online shopping in India?

109 responses

No
Yes
Nothing
easy return policies: a
Material of the product must be good
Security
Quality
Fast movement of delivery goods
Display actual quality
Need better service
Availability
Quality and Service

The customers who buy products online prefers good quality products at reasonable price, expects fastest delivery of product, ensures availability of products anytime, traders should provide safety of the product till it reaches the customer, after sales services should be provided, product return policies should be explained and followed so that customers will be able to buy the products and enjoy the benefits and promote the products by spreading positive message through ‘Word of Mouth’

Findings and Suggestions

1. As per the objectives of the paper based on online consumer behavior, it is clear that majority of the consumers prefer offline shopping, and rate Flipkart as the most used application. The respondents also mentioned that they prefer offline shopping when compared to Online with an majority from 109 respondents
2. The study also states that online shopping can be improved only through better services, quality of the material, availability and services after sales.
3. The survey also depicts the most common issues faced while online shopping such as Return policy, quality difference, size, and delay in time.
4. It also projects that quality of goods must be given most priority with delivery on time as majority from 109 respondents.
5. The paper states that the youth in Bangalore prefer online shopping only if the company takes all the suggestions that are preferred to satisfy the needs of the people.

Conclusion

Technology in the field of online shopping has made a significant progress over the years in order to provide the customers a better shopping experience and will have a greater progress in the coming years with many new technological implementations. The number of sites for online shopping will also increase in the coming days as per the demand of the customers. As per the research made it is clear that many of the customers have done online shopping but the rest are aware off but have never tried with it. The research also concludes that even though many respondents shop through online but majority of them prefer to shop offline because in online shopping they cannot feel or touch the product. Online shopping has brought many changes in the field of shopping where people are able to buy the products or it can be medicine or vegetables or grocery items through online. Online shopping has made the individuals to try with the new products that enter into the market with just one click. The research was made to know about how the customers are enjoying the online shopping or how it has been a drawback for them and the end results obtained includes that many of them are happy with the services provided whereas some are not. Therefore the technological impact on online shopping is more and is assumed to be still better in the coming future days.

Reference

1. Rahman Mohammed And Islam Mohammed (2018). Consumer Buying Behaviour Towards Online Shopping: An Emperical Study On Dhaka City Bangladesh. Cogent Business And Management, Volume-5, Issue- 1.
2. Kumar Amit (2014). Consumer Behaviour In Online Shopping: Astudy Of Aizanil, International Journal Of Business And Management Research (Ijbmr), Volume-1, Issue-3 Page 45-49.
3. Kaur Anupreet (2016). A Study Of Behavior Of Consumer Towards Online Shopping. Dictum, Volume-1 Issue-I.

4. Dani Jemila (2017). A Study On Consumer’s Attitude Towards Online Shopping. International Journal Of Research In Management And Business Studies (Ijrmbs 2017), Vol-4, Issue 3 (Spl2).
5. Wahil Normilia Nadia Nurul (2018). Why Consumers Are Hesitant To Shop Online. The Major Concern Towards Online Shopping, International Journal Of Academic Research In Business And Social Sciences, 8(9) ,1175- 1185.
6. [Http://Www.yourarticlelibrary.com/Marketing/Market-Segmentation/Consumer-Behaviour-Meaningdefinition-And-Nature-Of-Consumer-Behaviour/32301](http://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/Marketing/Market-Segmentation/Consumer-Behaviour-Meaningdefinition-And-Nature-Of-Consumer-Behaviour/32301)
7. [Https://Www.brandwatch.com/Blog/How-Understand-Influence-Consumer-Behavior/](https://www.brandwatch.com/Blog/How-Understand-Influence-Consumer-Behavior/)